

Kinetics and Mechanism of Chlorination of Aniline by Sodium *N*-Chlorobenzenesulphonamide in Hydrochloric Acid Medium†

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Kinetics of chlorination of aniline(S) by chloramine-B(CAB) in HCl medium obey the rate law

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAB}]}{dt} = k'[\text{CAB}][\text{H}^+]^{1.27}[\text{S}]^{0.4} + k''[\text{CAB}][\text{Cl}^-]^{0.7}[\text{S}]^{0.4}$$

The active species in the oxidation is RNH_2Cl^+ . Chloride ion catalyses the reaction. An order of dependence of 2.0 on the gross concentration of HCl is obtained, indicating mixed order kinetics with simultaneous catalysis of H^+ and Cl^- .

KINETICS of oxidation of substituted-benzyl alcohols¹, dimethylsulphoxide² and unsaturated alcohols^{3,4} by chloramine-B have been reported. Aniline is a parent substance for many dyes and drugs. In our systematic investigation on the mechanistic aspects of oxidation of some aromatic amines, simultaneous catalysis by H^+ and Cl^- were noted during the chlorination of aniline by chloramine-B in presence of HCl. These are reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Distilled aniline (B.D.H.) was used and its solution was prepared in ethanol. An aqueous solution of chloramine-B was standardised by the iodometric method. All other chemicals were of analytical grade. Kinetic studies were carried out at ionic strength of 0.5 M (NaClO_4) in 50% v/v ethanol at 30° under pseudo-first order condition. The rate of reaction was determined by estimating the unreacted CAB iodometrically.

The stoichiometry of the reaction under the present conditions (substrate in excess) was found to be 1 : 1 and the product was monochloroaniline (a mixture of *o*- and *p*-chloroaniline).

The products were detected by tlc (silica gel).

Results and Discussion

At constant $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.05 M) and [aniline] (0.1 M), a first order dependence of the rate on [CAB] is noted. The pseudo-first order rate constant k_ψ was $3.14 \pm 0.13 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. A plot of $\log k_\psi$ vs

$\log [\text{aniline}]$ gave a straight line of slope 0.4, indicating a fractional order dependence on substrate concentration (0.05-0.25 M). When $[\text{HCl}]$ was varied from 0.02 to 0.1 M, a plot of $\log k_\psi$ vs $\log [\text{HCl}]$ gave a straight line of slope 2.0. At constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (kept at 0.12 M by adding NaCl), variation of $[\text{H}^+]$ indicated an order of 1.27 as shown by the plot of $\log k_\psi$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$. Keeping $[\text{H}^+]$ constant at 0.05 M, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ was varied by adding NaCl (0.06-0.13 M) and a plot of $\log k_\psi$ vs $\log [\text{Cl}^-]$ gave a straight line of slope 0.7.

Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide, to the reaction mixture had no effect on the rate. Also, variation of ethanol had a negligible effect on the rate, indicating the absence of dielectric constant effects. Increase in the ionic strength of the medium from 0.5 to 1.0 M had a negligible effect. The activation parameters were $E_a = 55.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -75.4 \text{ JK}^{-1}$. Addition of acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture had no effect, indicating the absence of free radical species.

Chloramine-B ionises in aqueous solution^{3,4}. In acidified solutions, the possible chlorinating species^{3,4} are RNCl_2 , RNHCl and HOCl . The following scheme accounts for the experimental results.

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If $[CAB]_T = [RNCl^-] + [RNHCl] + [RNH_2Cl^+] + [X]$, then the rate law would be

$$\frac{-d \log [CAB]}{dt} = \frac{k_4 K_1 K_2 K_3 [S][H^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [H^+] \{1 + K_2 [H^+] + K_2 K_3 [H^+][S]\}} \quad (1)$$

Different workers⁵⁻⁸ have proposed the formation of *N*-chloramines in the chlorination of aromatic amines. The formation of *ortho*- and *para*-isomers in the halogenation of some aromatic primary amines have been reported^{9,10}. However, under the present experimental conditions, plausible mechanism has been proposed as described in Scheme 1.

where, $R = C_6H_4SO_2$

Scheme 1

Increase in the rate of reaction by the addition of chloride ion is similar to its effect observed in the Orton rearrangement of *N*-haloamides¹¹. The latter refers to the migration of chlorine from the side chain of a *N*-haloanilide or a ring substituted derivative of chloroamide to the ring in the presence of H^+ and Cl^- . The present results can be explained by the following scheme, where a nucleophilic attack by Cl^- on RNH_2Cl^+ is assumed, accounting for the catalytic effect of chloride ions.

The rate law at constant $[H^+]$ can be derived as,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_3 k_7 [CAB]_T [H^+]^2 [S][Cl^-]}{1 + K_1 [H^+] \{1 + K_2 [H^+] + K_2 K_3 [H^+][S]\} [Cl^-]} \quad (2)$$

When catalysis is effected simultaneously by H^+ and Cl^- , an order of 2.0 on the gross concentration of HCl is observed. This may be traced to a mixed order kinetics following the rate law,

$$-\frac{d[CAB]}{dt} = k'[CAB][H^+]^{1.27}[S]^{0.4} + k''[CAB][Cl^-]^{0.7}[S]^{0.4} \quad (3)$$

In the composite rate law, the first term accounts for H^+ catalysis and the second for Cl^- catalysis. Similar observations were made in the chlorination of substituted-phenols by chloramine- T^{12} .

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References

1. J. MUKHERJEE and K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1980, 676.
2. RANGASWAMY and H. S. YATHIRAJAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1981, 50, 757.
3. R. SWAMY, H. S. YATHIRAJAN and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1981, 26, 565.
4. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, RANGASWAMY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 47, 1826.
5. R. S. NEALE, R. G. SCHEPERS and M. R. WALSH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 8390.
6. P. HABERFIELD and D. PAUL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 87, 5502.
7. P. G. GASSMAN and G. A. CAMPBELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 2567.
8. V. M. S. RAMANUJAM and N. M. TRIEFF, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1977, 1275.
9. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTHI and M. D. PRASADRAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 485.
10. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTHI and M. D. PRASADRAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 1018.
11. E. S. GOULD, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1964 p 60.
12. V. BALASUBRAMANIAN and V. THIAGARAJAN, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1975, 7, 605.